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Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) update

Authors	Paola Ronzino, James Tierney
Contributors	
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Deliverable Abstract

Text (no more than 2-3 sentences)

This deliverable provides an overview of the development of the EOSC Partnership’s Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, or SRIA, during the 36 months of EOSC Focus. The report highlights key milestones, consultation processes, and strategic adaptations that have influenced the SRIA’s evolution. Given special attention are the periodic updates of the priority areas in the SRIA’s Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR), which serves as the broader EOSC community’s input to the European Commission’s Horizon Europe Work Programme.

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V.1.0	29/04/2025		Paola Ronzino James Tierney	0000-0002-6685-8267 0009-0006-7319-3378

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
GA	General Assembly
MAR	Multi-Annual Roadmap
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
The Partnership	The Horizon Europe European Co-programmed Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud

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Executive Summary

The current phase of implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC; 2021-2030) is taking place in the framework of the Horizon Europe European Co-programmed Partnership for EOSC. The Partnership's objectives are defined in the [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA), which is co-developed with the broader EOSC community and is co-owned by the European Commission (EC) and the EOSC Association (EOSC-A).

The development of the SRIA has been an iterative and collaborative process and has been shaped through continuous consultation with the broader EOSC community, ensuring alignment with the evolving research and innovation landscape.

The SRIA versions are iterative and updated with each new Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR), which constitutes Chapter 8 of the SRIA. The SRIA 1.3 (including MAR 2026-2027) builds further on SRIA 1.2 (including MAR 2025-2027), which builds on SRIA 1.1 (including MAR 2023-2024), which in turn builds on SRIA 1.0 (including MAR 2021-2022).

SRIA 1.1 was prepared prior to the start of EOSC Focus, however its finalisation in the fall of 2022 took place under EOSC Focus.

SRIA 1.2 introduced the MAR 2025-2027, which set the groundwork for future research priorities, informing the drafting of the INFRAEOSC calls in the Horizon Europe Work Programme for the corresponding years.

In 2024, SRIA 1.3 incorporated updated priorities for 2026-2027 following a comprehensive consultation process.

A comprehensive update to the SRIA, SRIA 2.0, is in progress and will define the strategic direction of EOSC post-2027. The updates will reflect EOSC's evolving governance structure and funding model, as well as general advancements in digital technologies and Open Science.

This deliverable provides an overview of the development of the SRIA during EOSC Focus, highlighting key milestones, consultation processes, and strategic adaptations that have influenced its evolution.

The EOSC Focus project has provided direct support to the EOSC-A Board of Directors and Secretariat in the preparation, administration and promotion of each of the community consultations for SRIA 1.2 (MAR 2025-2027), SRIA 1.3 (MAR 2026-2027), and SRIA 2.0. EOSC Focus has also provided direct support to the post-consultation analysis of the inputs and the strategic application of the outcomes of the three consultations.

1 Introduction

The [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#), or SRIA, is co-owned by EOSC-A and the European Commission, and is being developed in different iterations within the framework of the Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (the [EOSC Partnership](#)).

The SRIA outlines clear goals for developing EOSC to foster Open Science and enhance trust and reproducibility in research by creating a trusted, virtual, federated environment in Europe for storing, sharing, and reusing research outputs across disciplines and borders. This is envisaged to result in an improved pan-European research landscape with better discovery, access, interoperability, and utilisation of research outcomes for researchers and innovation stakeholders.

The EOSC Association works with the EOSC Task Forces¹ and the broader community to define Multi-Annual Roadmaps (MAR) that further guide the development of EOSC. Each update of the MAR is used by the European Commission as input to the corresponding Horizon Europe (HE) Work Programmes and therefore the updates are the Association's best instrument to influence the Commission's funding calls. This process is enshrined in Section 4 of the EOSC Partnership's [Memorandum of Understanding](#), in which the EC commits to duly taking into account EOSC-A's "input and advice" on the relevant research and innovation funding calls.

In the context of the EOSC Partnership, the funding periods for both the HE Work Programmes and the SRIA implementation stages are aligned from 2021 through 2027. Each stage defines a high-level objective for the period, and for each stage, priority areas are defined. Their prioritisation and scheduling reflect community feedback from the open consultation process.

The MAR 2025-2027, for example, was introduced with [SRIA 1.2](#) and presents the eight priority areas for "Stage 3" of the SRIA's implementation in paragraph 8.9. These priorities align with the HE Work Programme planning for the corresponding years, which includes a Work Programme for 2025, followed by separate Work Programmes for 2026 and 2027. MAR 2026-2027, introduced with [SRIA 1.3](#), provides a community update on those priorities for the corresponding HE Work Programmes.

SRIA 2.0, which remains in progress, will define the strategic direction for EOSC post-2027, reflecting EOSC's evolving governance structure, funding model, as well as general advancements in digital technologies and Open Science practices.

2 Establishing SRIA 1.2 and MAR 2025-2027

The MAR 2025-2027 is incorporated into SRIA 1.2, and builds upon previous roadmaps for Stage 1 (2021-2022) and Stage 2 (2023-2024). The update from SRIA 1.1 to SRIA 1.2 was an update of Chapter 8 of the original document where the MAR 2025-2027 is newly introduced.

MAR 2025-2027 focuses on eight priorities for 2025 (see SRIA 1.2 chapter 8.1), with preliminary guidance for 2026-2027. The MAR 2025-2027 priority areas and scheduling have been determined through community feedback obtained during an open consultation process facilitated by EOSC-A and supported by EOSC Focus.

¹ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces/>

The 13 EOSC-A Task Forces (2021-2023) began to provide input for the creation of the MAR 2025-2027 as early as autumn 2022. From autumn 2022 to spring 2023, MAR 2025-27 was produced by developing a set of proposed actions for all three years, but with a focus on the envisaged priorities for 2025.

The EOSC-A Board developed an initial list of relevant topics based on this input and shared it with the European Commission in December 2022. Further revisions were made in consultation with the Task Forces, and a draft MAR 2025-2027 was released for further consultation with the EOSC-A members and observers from 7 March to 24 April 2023.²

This EOSC-A consultation resulted in 652 community comments from 57 survey responses and several coordinated written responses from EOSC-A Mandated Organisations, Helmholtz Society members, the ESFRI Working Group and others.

With support of the EOSC Focus project, the many inputs and suggestions received were analysed, and the necessary adjustments were made to the text of the MAR. In parallel, seven standalone feedback documents were screened, and the validated comments were also incorporated into the draft MAR 2025-27. Once the comments had been examined and processing recommendations were formulated, the EOSC-A Board reviewed the suggestions and determined the subsequent steps.

A first, consolidated post-consultation version of the MAR 2025-2027 was shared with the Commission on 01 September 2023. The European Commission provided additional input at this stage, mainly on European-level priorities.

A first draft of SRIA 1.2, including MAR 2025–2027, was then shared with the Commission on 13 October 2023. It was adopted by the EOSC-A General Assembly at GA#7 in November 2023, and approved by the Partnership Board in their December 2023 meeting.

3 SRIA 1.3 and the MAR 2026-2027 updating and consultation process

In 2024, the European Commission made the decision to establish the 2025 HE Work Programme as a standalone one-year Work Programme. This provided EOSC-A with the opportunity to reassess and further elaborate its input for the final two years of Horizon Europe, 2026 and 2027.

The EOSC-A Board of Directors opened the process to update the MAR 2025-2027 in autumn 2024 by proposing new priorities for 2026-2027. The Board restructured the priorities into four new high-level areas, referred to as “Strategic Pillars”, rather than according to the SRIA’s three General Objectives, as was the case for previous versions of the MAR. The new set of high-level areas responded to developments in the EOSC landscape since SRIA 1.2 was produced, and presents a clearer picture of the proposed actions. The Strategic Pillars are:

Strategic Pillar 1: Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation

Strategic Pillar 2: Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI

Strategic Pillar 3: Ensuring research security and sovereignty

Strategic Pillar 4: Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond

² A full accounting of the consultation results and ensuing processing and analysis for MAR 2025-2027 is provided in Sections 8.2-8.4 of Chapter 8 of [SRIA 1.2](#).

Each Strategic Pillar was further subdivided into the three levels of EOSC implementation: European, national and institutional, as was the case for earlier versions of the MAR organised under the General Objectives. The overall number of priorities proposed in the updated MAR 2026-2027 was smaller than in previous versions, reflecting the clearer focus and higher definition that is emerging for EOSC.

The proposed update to MAR 2026-2027 from the EOSC-A Board was used as the basis for a public consultation, prepared with substantial support from EOSC Focus, which ran from 03 September to 24 September 2024. The 2024 survey received 51 responses, including more than 200 comments that were analysed by teams within EOSC Focus.³

All comments were analysed and assessed for the appropriate way to address them, and many resulted in changes to the proposed MAR 2026-2027. The alteration of the structure of the MAR into four “pre-organised” Strategic Pillars greatly increased the efficiency of processing the community feedback.

In October 2024 the updated set of priority actions for each Strategic Pillar was reviewed by a member of the EOSC Association Board. The complete set of updated actions was then subject to a final review by the Board to check for overall coherence and consistency, and then shared with the EC. The Commission’s input on the European priorities was taken on board, and MAR 2026-2027 was published as an annex to chapter 8 of [SRIA 1.3](#).

Fig. 1: Promo for MAR 2026-2027 consultation

SRIA 1.3, including MAR 2026-2027, was adopted by the EOSC-A 9th General Assembly in November 2024, and approved by the Partnership Board in the following month.

4 Towards SRIA 2.0: Defining the Future of EOSC

Recent developments around the implementation of EOSC have been considerable and are increasing in speed. The [kick-off of the EOSC Federation’s build-up phase](#) in March 2025, the [launch of the EOSC EU Node](#) in October 2024, the continuous deployment of [components and services](#) developed by [HE INFRAEOSC projects](#), and the evolution of [national and institutional ecosystems](#) have given rise to the need to formulate a new SRIA to guide EOSC’s further development.

The development of SRIA 2.0 is being led by the EOSC-A Board of Directors, with the support of EOSC Focus. The aim of the new SRIA is to guide EOSC’s implementation post-2027, when the governance and funding model for EOSC will enter a new phase.

³ A full accounting of the MAR 2026-2027 consultation process, results and analysis is provided in Sections 8.1 and 8.2 of [SRIA 1.3](#).

The first draft table of contents for SRIA 2.0 was developed by the EOSC-A Board of Directors and presented by EOSC-A President Karel Luyben at the EOSC Winter School in Thessaloniki in January 2024. The [outputs](#) captured at the Winter School workshops – which included the HE INFRAEOSC projects, the EOSC-A Task Force Co-Chairs and the EOSC-A Board – contributed to the further development of the outline.

Following the Winter School, the first draft table of contents was refined by the EOSC-A Board, who also developed the outline of SRIA 2.0, i.e., chapter descriptions and content items.

An online community consultation for the extended outline of SRIA 2.0 was facilitated by EOSC-A with the support of EOSC Focus. It opened on 2 April 2024 and closed on 5 May 2024. The EOSC Association organised three webinars to present the draft content and introduce the consultation procedure to the wider stakeholder community. Nearly 200 participants registered for the webinars, out of which 147 attended the sessions live. After the last webinar on 23 April 2024, a [recording](#) was posted on the EOSC Association’s YouTube channel to allow those who were not able to attend to benefit from the information shared during the webinars.

Fig. 2: Promo for SRIA 2.0 consultation

The SRIA 2.0 community consultation enabled members of the community to score the relevance of each chapter’s proposed contents and to suggest new content items.

In total, 72 responses were collected during the consultation, out of which 52 were submitted on behalf of an organisation, and the rest were submitted by individuals in their own names. Among the most active countries (Fig. 3) were Spain (13% of all collected responses), the Netherlands (11%), Norway (10%), and Switzerland (10%). The majority of responses (94%) were provided by the EOSC-A membership, and only 6% were submitted by organisations or individuals not affiliated with EOSC-A (Fig. 4). More than half of the respondents (54%) represent a research-performing organisation, and 36% represent a service-providing organisation (Fig. 5). The latter category includes Research Infrastructures.

Fig. 3: Responses submitted per country during SRIA 2.0 community consultation, shown as a percentage of all collected responses.

Fig. 4: EOOSC-A memberships status of organisations participating in SRIA 2.0 community consultation, shown as a percentage of all collected responses.

Fig. 5: Types of organisation participating in SRIA 2.0 community consultation, shown as a percentage of all collected responses.

The Board of Directors – again with the support of EOSC Focus – assessed and addressed the input received from the consultation and drafted the next version of the SRIA 2.0 extended outline. Where needed, subject matter experts were invited to participate. The first analysis was presented at EOSC-A's 8th General Assembly in May 2024.

Due to the ongoing discussions and activities around the build-up of the [EOSC Federation](#) and the future of EOSC post-2027, preparation of a mature draft of SRIA 2.0 was de-prioritised for 2024, and will be picked up again in summer 2025.

The further development of SRIA 2.0 will depend heavily on the direction taken by the Partnership's Tripartite Governance relative to the EOSC Federation's post-2027 governance and funding models. Pending the advancement of these discussions, it is expected that SRIA 2.0 will be completed before 2026. Targeted consultations with relevant groups will take place as the new chapters are drafted.

5 References

No	Description/Link
R1	SRIA 1.1 (Nov 2022): https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/SRIA-1.1-final.pdf
R2	SRIA 1.2 (Nov 2023): https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf
R3	SRIA 1.3 (Nov 2024): https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/20241031_SRIA_1.3_final_Annex.pdf
R4	EOSC Partnership MoU: https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/EOSC_Memorandum_30_July_2021-1.pdf
R5	SRIA & MAR page on eosc.eu: https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/